

PROJECT REPORT
ON
Account Management System

Submitted To
GAUTAM BUDDH TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY

in partial fulfilment of the requirements
for the degree of
Bachelor of Technology

Submitted to the Department of Computer Science and Engineering
Bharat Institute of Technology, Partapur by-pass road, Meerut
Gautam Buddha Technical University, Lucknow

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this submission is my own work and that, to the best of my knowledge and belief, it contains no material previously published or written by another person nor material which to a substantial extent has been accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma of the university or other institute of higher learning, except where due acknowledgment has been made in the text.

ABHINAV MITTAL
(0912810003)

Date: __/__/__

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that this Project Report entitled “**Account Management System**” which is submitted by Abhinav Mittal in the partial fulfilment, for the award of degree of Bachelor of Technology in Department of Computer Science & Engineering, of BHARAT INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, Meerut, affiliated to GAUTAM BUDDH TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY, Lucknow; is carried out by her under my supervision.

The matter embodied in this Project Work has not been submitted earlier for award of any degree or diploma in any university/institution to the best of our knowledge and belief.

(Mr. Pankaj Rana)

Project Guide

(Associate Prof. Kshitiz Saxena)

Project Coordinator and Head of the Department (CSE)

Date: __/__/____

ABSTRACT

Account Management System is software developed for daily student attendance in schools, colleges and institutes. It facilitates to access the attendance information of a particular student in a particular class. The information is sorted by the operators, which will be provided by the teacher for a particular class. This system will also help in evaluating attendance eligibility criteria of a student.

In the present system all work is done on paper. The whole session attendance is stored in register and at the end of the session the reports are generated and the students who don't have 75% attendance get a notice.

The existing system is not user friendly because the retrieval of data is very slow and data is not maintained efficiently. We require more calculations to generate the report so it is generated at the end of the session. And the students not get a single chance to improve their attendance. All calculations to generate report are done manually so there is greater chance of errors. Existing system requires lot of paper work. Loss of even a single register/record led to difficult situation because all the papers are needed to generate the reports. Every work is done manually so we cannot generate report in the middle of the session or as per the requirement because it is very time consuming.

The proposed system is user friendly because the retrieval and storing of data is fast and data is maintained efficiently. Moreover the graphical user interface is provided in the proposed system, which provides user to deal with the system very easily. Reports can be easily generated in the proposed system so user can generate their report as per the requirement (monthly) or in the middle of the session. User can give the notice to the students so he/she become regular

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview :-

Account Management System basically has four main modules for proper functioning:-

- **Admin:** This has right for creating space for new batch. Any entry of new faculty, updating in status of account. He can also delete any individual from database.
For generating, viewing, editing and mailing pay slips of employees.
Admin have all the privileges in the system he/she can edit and update all the entities of the system and have also have the feature of live search which make his/her work easier.
- **Manager:** He is responsible for generating, viewing, editing and mailing pay slips of employees.
- **Faculty:** A faculty can search any student from any stream, view and print-out his/her pay slip.
- **Student:** A student can see his details from anywhere, change his login password.
Student have the least privileges he/she can see only his details and can also send a query if see any mistake in his details.

1.2 Objective:

The purpose of developing Account management system is to computerized the traditional managing things in any institution. What we generally see in a system where accounts are managed is that there is a lot paper work and lot of redundancy in the working structure of the organisation. So the most basic objective of this proposed system is to overcome these problems which a traditional system faces.

Another purpose for developing this software is to access and edit information of individuals in the institution at real time i.e. view the information regarding individuals in no time and can change their values and data at the same time which will give the user a real time experience.

One of the most unique feature of this system for dealing with situations like redundancy and effective record maintenance is the feature of payslip management. Through this feature of payslip management one can easily generate payslip for their employees with proper record maintenance, moreover the employees to which these payslips are related, can access these records electronically and can print their hardcopies for further purpose.

Another feature involved which is main part of objective is the search in records. Searching in no time within huge sets of records was one of the main objective of this system which is effectively handled thorough the feature of live searching through the records.

1.3 Scope

The scope of this project is very widespread. This system is developed to handle the full requirements of an account management of an organisation. This system as developed keeping into consideration the working of the system within a college, covers all the basic aspects which can be managed electronically.

The scope of this system can be extended enormously. Starting with the basic module of a student, features such as daily attendance update, sessional marks updates with subject name, automatic short attendance letter generation, remarks option for student and many other can be easily implemented with this system.

Coming on to the next module of faculty the scope includes daily attendance update, attendance records maintenance, sessional marks records maintenance, payslip records maintenance, time table generation and schedule maintenance are the some basic features which encompasses the scope of this module.

Manager module scope tends to features like payslip record maintenance, faculty details maintenance, management of records and many other.

The admin module being the strongest module in the terms of privileges has scope like management of users in the system on air, activate/inactivate user on click of a button, effective record maintenance.

CHAPTER 2

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Current system says today organisation people do many paper work and then they have to assemble that documents which makes their work hectic and also misplace of documents happens a lot due to human nature

2.1 Proposed system

- The system being developed is economic with respect to School or Collage's point of view. It is cost effective in the sense that has eliminated a lot of paper work.
- The system is also time effective because the searching and editing is done with a just a click. Payrolls are no exception.
- The result obtained contains minimum errors and are highly accurate as the data is required.
- The technical requirement for the system is economic and it does not use any other additional Hardware and software.
- The system working is quite easy to use and learn due to its simple but attractive interface. User requires no special training for operating the system.
- Increase the transparency in the working structure of the college.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

As per the requirement our software is a narrow network based to avoid traffic problems. The software has following modules:

Admin

Manager

Faculty

Student

3.1 Admin:

Education administrators organise and manage the administration, support systems and activities that facilitate the effective running of an educational institution. The majority are based in higher or further education (HE or FE), with opportunities also available in schools and private colleges.

Administrators work in areas such as admissions, quality assurance, data management and examinations or in a specialist department such as finance, careers or human resources. All of these can be either centrally based or within faculties, departments or other smaller units.

Admin is an an person who has full privillage to the software.

he/she has right for creating space for new batch. Any entry of new faculty, updating in status of account. He can also delete any individual from database.

For generating, viewing, editing and mailing pay slips of employees

As by the help of pagination he/she can view all the person existing in the system. Can also add, delete or modify an entry.

3.2 Manager:

A manager is a person whose job is to manage something, such as a business, a restaurant, or a institution.

He is responsible for generating, viewing, editing and mailing pay slips of employees. He is provided with the access of calculating functions can also add some sort of details of the existing faculty and can figure out any extra taxes or allowances provided to them.

3.3 Faculty:

A faculty is a division within a university comprising one subject area, or a number of related subject areas (for the North American usage, referring to academic staff, see "Faculty (academic staff)"). In American usage such divisions are generally referred to as colleges (e.g., "college of arts and sciences") or schools (e.g., "school of business"), but may also mix terminology (e.g., Harvard University has a "faculty of arts and sciences" but a "law school").

A faculty can search any student from any stream, view and print-out his/her pay slip. Faculty can also enter the marks of their students. faculty has the authority to update the attendance of the student can also do some changes for the student they are also allotted with facilities to active or inactive any student account.

3.4 Student:

A student is a learner, or someone who attends an educational institution. In some nations, the English term (or its cognate in another language) is reserved for those who attend university, while a schoolchild under the age of eighteen is called a pupil in English (or an equivalent in other languages), although in the United States a person enrolled in grades K–12 is often called a student. In its widest use, student is used for anyone who is learning, including mid-career adults who are taking vocational education or returning to university. Student have the least privileges he/she can see only his details and can also send a query if see any mistake in his details.

CHAPTER 2

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

Software Requirement:

1	Data Base	MySql
2	Language	Php , Java
3	Script	JScript, AJAX , JQuery , HTML

System Requirement:

1	RAM	256MB
2	MEMORY	40GB
3	PROCESSOR	Intel p4 minimum
4	Operating system	Windows XP and above

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM PLANNING

Gantt Chart

Select Columns <input type="checkbox"/>				Q4, 2012	Q1, 2013			Q2, 2013
#	Name	Start Date	End Date	December	January	February	March	April
24	Design	Mon 02/11/13	Fri 02/22/13					
25	▼ 4th Module(faculty)	Wed 02/27/13	Wed 04/03/13					
26	Data base	Wed 02/27/13	Mon 03/04/13					
27	print pay slip	Mon 03/04/13	Tue 03/12/13					
28	new task	Mon 03/11/13	Wed 03/20/13					
29	Pagination	Wed 03/20/13	Wed 03/27/13					
30	edit student	Wed 03/27/13	Wed 04/03/13					
31								
32								
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CHAPTER 4

DEDICATED LIFECYCLE OF PROJECT

4.1 USE CASE DIAGRAM

Figure 3-1: Use Case Diagram for “Account Management System”

USE CASE REPORT:

- **Administrator:** Responsible for maintaining all the databases, editing profiles, adding new user and maintaining site, user details and login.
 - **Login:** The administrator must be logged into the system to gain authentication.
 - **Maintain Site:** The site and database will be maintained.
 - **Update Members:** Administrator can add, delete and modify the profile of the users.
 - **Backup/ Recovery:** The administrator is responsible to create backup and recover the system in case of failure.

- **Manager:** Manager has the privilege to.
 - **Login:** The user must be logged into the system to gain privileges.
 - **Edit Profile:** Users can delete and modify faculty profile.
 - **Generate payslip:** Can generate faculty details.
 - **Add details:** Can add some of the faculty details.

- **Faculty:** Faculty users can view site contents and register students profile
 - **Login:** The user must be logged into the system to gain privileges.
 - **View Site Contents:** Site contents such as status of student
 - **Register:** Add marks of student
 - **Edit Profile:** Edit the profile of student.
 - **View payslip:** Can view his/her payslip.

- **Student:** Student has privilege to see his profile.
 - **Login Profile:** The user must be logged into the system to gain privileges.
 - **View Profile:** Student can view only his/her profile.

4.2 DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

Level 1 DFD

Level 2 DFD

4.3 E-R DIAGRAM

An entity-relationship (ER) diagram is a specialised graphic that illustrates the relationship between entities in a database. ER diagrams often use symbols to represent three different types of information.

Boxes are commonly used to represent entities. Diamonds are used to represent relationships and ovals are used to represent attributes.

Figure 3-2: E-R Diagram for “Account Management System”

CHAPTER 5

DATABASE TABLES

Login Table

S.no	Field name	Data type	Description
1	Pid	int(250)	Store an auto increment value
2	<u>Email</u>	Varchar(20)	Store email corresponding to pid
3	Password	Varchar(20)	Store password corresponding to pid
4	Fname	Varchar(20)	Store first name corresponding to pid
5	Lname	Varchar(20)	Store last name corresponding to pid
6	Role	Varchar(20)	Store role of the user corresponding to pid
7	Status	Varchar(20)	Store account status Corresponding to pid

Faculty Table

S.no	Field name	Data type	Description
1	Pid	Int(250)	Store last name corresponding to pid
2	Name	Varchar(20)	Name of Faculty
3	Pslip	Mediumblob	Payslip of faculty in pdf format
4	<u>Email</u>	Varchar(30)	Email of faculty
5	Date_of_joining	Date	Date of joining of faculty
6	Designation	Varchar(30)	Designation of faculty

Student Table

S.no	Field name	Data type	Description
1	Name	Varchar(20)	Name of student
2	Branch	Varchar(20)	Branch of student
3	Roll no.	Varchar(10)	Roll no. Of student
4	Date of birth	Date	Date of birth of student
5	Contact no.	Varchar(10)	Contact no. Of student
6	Guardian no.	Varchar(10)	Contact no. Of guardian
7	Guardian address	Varchar(100)	Address of guardian
8	<u>Email</u>	Varchar(30)	Email of student

Sec table

S.no	Field name	Data type	Description
1	Sessional	Int(3)	Sessional no.
2	Semester	Int(3)	Semester no.
3	Sub1	Int(30)	Sub1 marks
4	Sub2	Int(30)	Sub2 marks
5	Sub3	Int(30)	Sub3 marks
6	Sub4	Int(30)	Sub4 marks
7	Sub5	Int(30)	Sub5 marks
8	<u>Email</u>	varchar(30)	Email of student

Attend table

S.no	Name	Varchar(30)	Name of student
1	<u>Email</u>	Varchar(30)	Email of student
2	Jan	Float	January month attendance
3	Feb	Float	February month attendance
4	Mar	Float	Mar month attendance
5	April	Float	April month attendance
6	May	Float	May month attendance
7	June	Float	June month attendance
8	July	Float	July month attendance
9	Aug	Float	August month attendance
10	Sep	Float	September month attendance
11	Oct	Float	October month attendance
12	Nov	Float	November month attendance
13	Dec	Float	December month attendance

CHAPTER 6

METHODOLOGY ADOPTED AND SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

During the integration and test stage, the software artifacts, online help, and test data are migrated from the development environment to a separate test environment. At this point, all test cases are run to verify the correctness and completeness of the software. Successful execution of the test suite confirms a robust and complete migration capability. During this stage, reference data is finalized for production use and production users are identified and linked to their appropriate roles. The final reference data and production user list are compiled into the Production Initiation plan

6.1 Testing

The process of executing a system with intent of finding an error. Testing is defined as the process in which defects are identified, isolated, subjected for rectification and ensured that product is defect free in order to Quality is defined as justification of the requirements Defect is nothing but deviation from the requirements Defect is nothing but bug. Testing --- The presence of bugs testing can demonstrate the presence of bugs, but not their absence Debugging and Testing are not the same thing! Testing is a systematic attempt to break a program or the AUTO Debugging is the art or method of uncovering why the script /program did not execute properly.

6.2 Testing Methodologies

Black box Testing: is the testing process in which tester can perform testing on an application without having any internal structural knowledge

of application. Usually Test Engineers are involved in the black box testing. White box Testing: is the testing process in which tester can perform testing on an application with having internal structural knowledge. Usually The Developers are involved in white box testing.

6.3 Test Planning:

1. Test Plan is defined as a strategic document which describes the procedure how to perform various testing on the total application in the most efficient way.
2. This document involves the scope of testing,
3. Objective of testing,
4. Areas that need to be tested,
5. Areas that should not be tested,
6. Scheduling Resource Planning,
7. Areas to be automated, various testing tools

6.4 Result Analysis:

1. Expected Value: is nothing but expected behavior of application.
2. Actual value: is nothing but actual behavior of Application Bug Tracing: Collect all the failed cases, prepare documents. Reporting: Prepare document (status of the application)

6.5 TCD (Test Case Document):

Test Case Document Contains Test Scope (or) Test objective Test Scenario
Test Procedure Test case

6.6 Functional Testing:

The functions that a system, subsystem or component are to perform may be described in work products such as a requirements specification, use cases, or a functional specification, or they may be undocumented. The functions are “what” the system does. A type of functional testing, security testing, investigates the functions (e.g. a firewall) relating to detection of threats, such as viruses, from malicious outsiders. Another type of functional testing, interoperability testing, evaluates the capability of the software product to interact with one or more specified components or systems.

6.7 Structural Testing:

Structural testing is white box testing, not black box testing, since black boxes are considered opaque and do not permit visibility into the code. Structural testing is also known as clear box testing, also known as glass box testing. Structural testing is a way to test software with knowledge of the internal workings of the code being tested. Structural testing may be performed at all test levels. Structural techniques are best used after specification-based techniques, in order to help measure the thoroughness of testing through assessment of coverage of a type of structure. Structural testing approaches can also be applied at system, system integration or acceptance testing levels (e.g. to business models or menu structures).

6.8 Stress Testing:

In software testing, "System stress test" refers to tests that put a greater emphasis on robustness, availability, and error handling under a heavy load, rather than on what would be considered correct behavior under normal circumstances. In particular, the goals of such tests may be to ensure the software does not crash in conditions of insufficient

computational resources (such as memory or disk space), unusually high concurrency, or denial of service attacks. Examples: A web server may be stress tested using scripts, bots, and various denial of service tools to observe the performance of a web site during peak loads. There is some confusion about the Load Vs Stress testing, main difference will be in the focus of the testing Load test centered towards entire environment and DB and measuring the response time, whereas Stress test focus mainly on some identified transactions and pushing to a level so as to break transaction or systems. During stress testing, if entities/transactions are selectively stressed, the database may not experience much load at all, but those transactions are heavily stressed. On the other hand during Load testing database experience heavy load and entities/transactions identified for stress testing may not get much stressed. "System stress testing" popularly called as Stress testing is loading the concurrent users over and beyond to the level system can handle, so it breaks at the weakest link with in the entire system.

TEST CASES

TEST CASE	DESCRIPTION	DESIRED RESULT	ACTUAL RESULT
RTest1	Checking of availability of ID which user wants to Login	If ID is available then then login into account	If ID is available then a then login into account
RTest2	The password which user wants for his/her Login corresponding ID should be in database with corresponding id.	Login into corresponding account	Login into corresponding account
RTest3	The user is supposed to choose the correct role while login	If incorrect role selected message displayed choose the correct role.	If incorrect role selected message displayed choose the correct role.
CHTest1	A user can change password of his/her account.	A user can change the password of his/her account. The user needs to re-enter password and enter new desired password with one confirm password fields.	A user can change the password of his/her account. The user needs to re-enter password and enter new desired password with one confirm password fields.
BNTest1	A user can navigate through the links or buttons.	When a user click on a button or link then it should perform the corresponding functionality.	When a user click on a button or a link then it should perform the corresponding functionality.
LSTest1	User information should display on page.	When a user login through ID and password, user information display on page.	When a user login through ID and password, user information display on page.
ADMTest1	Administrator could modify details and database.	Admin update details and also database according to his/her requirements.	Admin update details and also database according to his/her requirements.

CHAPTER 7

MODULAR INTERACTION

Figure 7-1: Login Module

Figure 7-2: add_faculty details

Figure 7-3 add_Student_Details

Figure 7-4 add_user

Figure 7-5 Change Password

Figure 7-6 Generate payslip

Figure 7-7 Live search

Figure 7-8 Login

Figure 7-9 Logout

Figure 7-10 Pagination

Figure 7-11 Print Payslip

CHAPTER 8

SNAPSHOTS

Figure 8-1: Homepage for “Account management system”

Firefox You are welcome user localhost / localhost / project / login ...

localhost/membershipsite1/index.php

Most Visited Getting Started

Welcome Arjun | [Change Password](#) | [Logout](#)

Refresh Add New User

---MEMBER DETAILS---

UID	First Name	Last Name	E-mail	Role	Status	Delete
3	Arjun	Singh	arjun.hanu@gmail.com	admin	active	X
5	Avin	Agarwal	avin.cool@gmail.com	manager	active	X
4	Avin	Agarwal	avin.kumar@gmail.com	faculty	active	X
2	Avin	Agarwal	avin2cool@gmail.com	student	active	X
6	Abhinav	Mittal	marianabhinav@gmail.com	faculty	inactive	X

First Previous **1** 2 Next Last Go Page 1 of 2

Figure 8-2: Admin module in Account Management system

Firefox You are welcome user localhost / localhost / project / login ...

localhost/membershipsite1/manager.php

Welcome Avin | [Change Password](#) | [Logout](#)

Search Add Faculty Details Refresh Print Payslip Generate Payslip

---MEMBER DETAILS---

UID	First Name	Last Name	E-mail	Role	Status	Delete
4	Avin	Agarwal	avin.kumar@gmail.com	faculty	active	X
6	Abhinav	Mittal	marianabhinav@gmail.com	faculty	inactive	X

First Previous **1** Next Last Go Page 1 of 1

Figure 8-3: Manager module in account management System

Firefox You are welcome user localhost / localhost / project / login ...

localhost/membershipsite1/faculty.php

Welcome Abhinav | [Change Password](#) | [Logout](#)

Search any student name Add marks Refresh View Payslip Add Details

---MEMBER DETAILS---

UID	First Name	Last Name	E-mail	Role	Status	Delete
2	Avin	Agarwal	avin2cool@gmail.com	student	active	X
1	Abhinav	Mittal	marianabhinav@yahoo.com	student	active	X

First Previous **1** Next Last Go Page 1 of 1

Figure 8-4: Faculty module for “Account Management System”

STUDENT DETAILS
Name: Avin Agarwal
Branch: CSE
Roll no: 0912810028
DOB: 1992-08-30
Contact no: 9808090844
Guardian name: Vipin Agarwal
Guardian address: a 30 vaishali colony,meerut

SESSIONAL DETAILS
Sessional: 2
Semester: 7
Sub1: 29
Sub2: 28
Sub3: 26
Sub4: 25
Sub5: 28

ATTENDANCE DETAILS 2013	JAN: 70	FEB: 76	MAR: 76	APRIL:76	MAY:76	JUNE:76	JULY:76	AUG:76	SEP:76	OCT:76	NOV:76	DEC:67
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Figure 8-5: Student module for “Account Management System”

Figure 8-6: LIVE SEARCH feature for a members.

---MEMBER DETAILS---

First Name	Last Name	E-mail	Role	Status	Delete
Abhinav	Mittal	marianabhinav@yahoo.com	student	active	X
Arjun	Singh	arjun91@gmail.com	faculty	inactive	X
Avin	Agarwal	avin2cool@gmail.com	manager	active	X
Arjun	Singh	arjun.hanu@gmail.com	admin	active	X
Avin	Kumar	avin.agarwal91@gmail.com	faculty	inactive	X

Figure 8-7: PAGINATION feature for a members.

Welcome Avin | [Change Password](#) | [Logout](#)

Refresh	Print Payslip	Generate Payslip
Employee Id:	<input type="text"/>	
Basic Salary:	<input type="text"/>	
Allowance (%):	<input type="text"/>	
CTC :	<input type="text"/>	
TOTAL PAYABLE:	<input type="text" value="0"/>	
	Generate !!	

Figure 8-8: GENERATE PAYSLIP option for manager.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with a search bar containing 'Google' and a 'Bookmarks' section. The page header reads 'Welcome Abhinav | [Change Password](#) | [Logout](#)'. The main content area contains a form with three input fields: 'Current Password' (with three dots indicating a masked password), 'New Password', and 'Confirm Password'. A 'Submit' button is located at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 8-9: CHANGE PASSWORD option for members

[Welcome Avin](#) | [Change Password](#) | [Logout](#)

Name:
 Branch:
 Roll no:
 Date of Birth:
 Contact no:
 Gaurdian Name:
 Gaurdian Address:
 E-mail:

---MEMBER DETAILS---

UID	First Name	Last Name	E-mail	Role	Status	Delete
2	Avin	Agarwal	avin2cool@gmail.com	student	active	X
1	Abhinav	Mittal	marianabhinav@yahoo.com	student	active	X

Page 1 of 1

Figure 8-10: Faculty Page

Figure 8-11: Admin Page

Pay Slip

Employee id : 6

Name : Abhinav

Designation :

Date of joining : 0000-00-00

Salary : 12666

Allowances : 2

Cost to company : 6

Total amount : 12406.68

Figure 8-12: PAYS LIP format for emp

localhost/phpmyadmin/index.php?db=project&token=867ab4b14e76ad2da48cbaaa9c914ceb

phpMyAdmin

Database: project (5)

localhost > project > faculty

Showing rows 0 - 1 (~2¹ total, Query took 0.0004 sec)

```

SELECT *
FROM `faculty`
LIMIT 0, 30

```

Profiling [Edit] [Explain SQL] [Create PHP Code] [Refresh]

Show: 30 row(s) starting from record # 0
in horizontal mode and repeat headers after 100 cells

Sort by key: None

+ Options

	←T→	pid	name	pslip	email	date_of_joining	designation	
<input type="checkbox"/>			4	Avin	[BLOB - 1.1KiB]	avin.kumar@gmail.com	2012-04-30	Associate Professor
<input type="checkbox"/>			6	Abhinav	[BLOB - 1.0KiB]	marianabhinav@gmail.com	2000-12-30	assistant professor

Check All / Uncheck All With selected:

Show: 30 row(s) starting from record # 0
in horizontal mode and repeat headers after 100 cells

Query results operations

Print view Print view (with full texts) Export CREATE VIEW

Bookmark this SQL query

Figure 8-13 Faculty table

localhost/phpmyadmin/index.php?db=project&token=867ab4b14e76ad2da48cbaaa9c914ceb

Getting Started

Database

Showing rows 0 - 5 (~6¹ total, Query took 0.0004 sec)

```
SELECT *
FROM 'login'
LIMIT 0 , 30
```

Profiling [Edit] [Explain SQL] [Create PHP Code] [R

Show : 30 row(s) starting from record # 0

in horizontal mode and repeat headers after 100 cells

Sort by key: None

+ Options

			pid	email	password	fname	lname	role	status
<input type="checkbox"/>			3	arjun.hanu@gmail.com	123	Arjun	Singh	admin	active
<input type="checkbox"/>			5	avin.cool@gmail.com	123	Avin	Agarwal	manager	active
<input type="checkbox"/>			4	avin.kumar@gmail.com	123	Avin	Agarwal	faculty	active
<input type="checkbox"/>			2	avin2cool@gmail.com	123	Avin	Agarwal	student	active
<input type="checkbox"/>			6	marianabhinav@gmail.com	123	Abhinav	Mittal	faculty	active
<input type="checkbox"/>			1	marianabhinav@yahoo.com	abc	Abhinav	Mittal	student	active

Check All / Uncheck All With selected:

Show : 30 row(s) starting from record # 0

in horizontal mode and repeat headers after 100 cells

Query results operations

Print view Print view (with full texts) Export CREATE VIEW

Figure 8-14 Login table

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION

In the present scenario a lot of paper work needed to be done which leads to inefficient usage of our resources and a lack of transparency is also seen in the management.

- A platform having information about the institution will help it in managing the organization centrally as well as in a distributive manner.
- Different privilege facility will minimize the risk of its misuse.
- Online make it easy to work for institution at our home also.
- As everything used in this project is open source so no money is needed in buying license for using this.

CHAPTER 10

REFERENCE

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